

APPLICATION OF MODERN SCIENTIFIC METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE

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Abstract: *Science is not a concept that emerged yesterday or today. The earth we live in, the living nature in it, the humanity created, the science, the sense of knowing what humanity needs for its own benefit. Over the centuries, as thinking has expanded, so has knowledge and research.*

Key words: *Pedagogy, child-watching, methods, pedagogical techniques, technical means.*

The concepts of education and pedagogy ("child-watching") began to appear in the centers of civilization, such as ancient Egypt, Greece and Rome. To date, the term pedagogical technologies, interactive methods are actively and widely used in practice in order to improve the educational process, to make it easier and more convenient to master, to provide the student with a solid knowledge.

In particular, the concept of pedagogical technology originated in the twentieth century and is still in its infancy. If in the 30s of the last century in the educational process were used methods and tools as pedagogical techniques, in the 50s the tradition of organizing the educational process by technical means, and in the 60s the programming of teaching activities formed.

As such, I would also like to quote BL Farberman: Pedagogical technology is a new approach to the educational process and an expression of socio-engineering consciousness in pedagogy. It is a social phenomenon associated with the standardization of the pedagogical process on the basis of technical capabilities and human technical thinking, and the development of its optimal design.

No matter what the field, no matter what the subject, teaching with a variety of modern methods increases the possibilities and encourages the learner to accelerate in a particular science (or field) by gaining interest. In particular, there are three types of modern lessons:

- 1) lessons on new knowledge of the native language;
- 2) lessons to reinforce the past;
- 3) knowledge and skills testing lessons.

Of course, in each lesson, the teacher gives the students new knowledge, and the expected mastery of the knowledge is the expected result! To achieve this, you should not just use an outdated, rigorous method used by the teacher.

Instead, use an interesting and convenient method for the listener (student). The lesson has a way, a direction, a plan using modern methods. For example, pedagogical technologies are classified according to the following criteria: level of application; on a philosophical basis; on the main development factor; about the concept of skill; according to personal characteristics; by direction; by content feature; by type of management; child-centered approach; frequently used methods; by student categories.

The individual characteristics of the students should be taken into account when using different methods, because according to the individual characteristics, a person shows good results in a fast-growing field.

For instance, even if a student has an opinion, he or she will not be able to express his or her opinion freely. In this case, the use Ice Breaker, Osborne's Thought Attack, Step-by-Step, Scarab, and 3x4 can be effective.

Some students find it difficult to generalize and describe in writing using the Venus diagram, BBB chart, and Zig-Zag method.

The teaching process should not be based on superficial knowledge, but should be based on the "seeing and knowing" method throughout the lesson. In fact, it is the person who quickly remembers what he sees. Given that this method is more useful in the natural sciences, knowledge is better mastered on the basis of curiosity.

Also, some of the methods discussed above will help the student to think freely and increase their interest in future topics. Including, 3x4 technology teaches the ability to think about a specific topic individually or in small groups, to find a solution, to choose from a large number of ideas, to summarize the selected ideas, to express them. The "Creative" method is of a research nature and develops students' goal-oriented creative thinking.

It is also important to note that the organization of the educational process between the student and the teacher on an equal footing (inclusive) facilitates the process of learning the subject.

Motives, processes, and outcomes are key components of pedagogical technology that make learning easier and closer to the goal. Likewise, examples of interactive teaching methods: The method of working in small groups, the method of educational discussion, who knows more? Method, imaginary travel method, third surplus method, mail method, three answers to one question method, spelling relay method; Modeling method, demonstration method, critical thinking method, case study method, everyone teaches everyone, debate method, collaborative lesson method, differentiated lesson method, icebreaker method, writing and a way to develop critical thinking through reading.

In generally speaking, the interest in the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process in ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education is growing, one of the reasons for this, while traditional education has so far taught

students to acquire only ready-made knowledge, modern technology allows them to search, independently study, analyze, and even draw their own conclusions.

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